

IMPROVING SPEAKING AND LISTENING: STRATEGIES FOR ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract: Learning to speak necessarily involves the formation of skills to build up various types of invocations: message, persuasion, description, approval, etc., to use a variety of questions, the ability to convey the content of what you read. Teaching a foreign language can make a significant contribution to the development of educational and communicative skills, since in the process of mastering speech in English, these skills, of necessity, become the object of increased attention.

Keyin words: speaking, activity, motivation, foreign language, communication,

Speaking as an activity. Speaking is one of the types of activity; but speaking is a speech activity, therefore, it has special characteristics, for example: motivation, activity, purposefulness, connection with activity, connection with the communicative function of thinking, connection with personality and others. I would like to elaborate on motivation, activity, purposefulness and connection with the communicative function of thinking.

Motivation. Speaking is always motivated. Based on there are two types of need for communicative

Motivation: a) the need for communication as such, b) the need to commit this particular speech act. In the field of teaching foreign languages, the equal importance of the teacher’s professional language competence and the factor of taking into account the characteristics of students, in particular, their motivation, which include interests, needs, aspirations, etc. Is emphasized. “The learning process consists of three components of equal importance: a) the teacher and his skills; b) the student and his aspiration; c) the subject, the assimilation of which must be ensured”. Situational motivation educates the learner’s need for communication in general, creates a

constant motivational readiness – an extremely complex factor of successful participation in communication and, therefore, important for establishing a speech partnership. The absence of the status of speech partners in the relationship between students and teachers stems precisely from the lack of communicative motivation.

Activity. Speaking is always an active process, because in it the attitude of the speakers to the surrounding reality is manifested. This attitude takes place not only when a person speaks, but also when he listens to the interlocutor (internal activity). What is meant here is not the side of it that is aimed at listening, at understanding the interlocutor's speech, but the activity of reaction to what is

Perceived: passing evaluation of statements, partial planning of one's replica, etc. It is the activity that ensures the verbal behavior of the interlocutor, which is so important for achieving the learning goal. "If, in the process of teaching, students are united with each other or with the teacher only by the fact that they are participants in the learning process, an "interlocutor", and therefore there will be neither speech activity nor initiative".

Purposefulness. Speaking is always purposeful, since any statement pursues some purpose. The aimless utterance of some sentences is pronouncing, not speaking. The speaker always wants to achieve some goal with his statement: to convince or dissuade his interlocutor, to arouse sympathy or anger him, to support his opinion or, conversely, to ridicule him and so on. Such goals can be called communicative tasks. Their solution is the purposefulness of speaking, that is, the subordination of all its qualities (as an activity and as a product) to the fulfillment of the task set in communication.

Therefore, speaking can be truly purposeful only when it has all the necessary qualities that integrate into purposefulness. Connection with the communicative function of thinking. The process of speech activity is closely related to the activity of thinking. But what happens in the process of thinking as "an active process of reflecting the objective world in concepts, judgments, theories" is not identical to what happens in the mental activity associated with speaking. I believe that the case here is not in the level of language.

Proficiency: you can perfectly speak the language, communicate fluently in it, but not be able to think in a foreign language. Speaking is a constant solution of communicative speech-thinking tasks. And if we want to teach speaking, then we should do it on similar tasks. V.A. Kan-Kalik notes that "a teacher who does not know the structure and laws of pedagogical communication has poorly developed communicative abilities and communicative culture in general". Speaking as a

product. All the qualities of speaking as an activity provide the conditions for creating a speech product (utterances of any level), which also has certain qualities.

1. *Structurality*. This quality is manifested in the fact that speech units have their own structure, which is inherent in any of their levels: word forms, word combinations, phrases, super-phrasal units, the whole text. The knowledge of the structure of all levels and the definition of speech patterns on this basis is of paramount importance for teaching speaking, since each of the levels gives the student a lot of difficulties and is a source of errors. This is especially true of the level of phrases.

2. *Consistency*. The logic of speaking is understood as its property, which is provided by a certain sequence of presentation, “that is, the presentation of a number of thoughts, facts connected both internally, due to the semantic connection between them, and externally, with the help of special means of language”. Consistency requires special training. This is especially true with regard to statements of the level of super-phrasal unity and the level of the text.

3. *Informative*. As V.N. Trostnikov wrote: “Information is not a characteristic of a message, but of the relationship between a message and its consumer”. This means that the same message can be informative for one participant of communication and uninformative for another. The level of this informativeness is determined: for the interlocutor – by the value of the message for him as a person, for the speaker, obviously, by the measure of the impact on the interlocutor. If speaking was not informative, we would not have speech partners in communication: they would not be interested in us, because they would not hear anything new from us.

4. *Expressiveness*. This quality of the product of speaking, as well as informativeness, serves its effectiveness. Intonation and logical stress (expressiveness parameters) when teaching speaking are not a luxury, but an important means stimulation of interest in the learning process itself, as they clearly show the student the role of these components in expressing his communicative intentions, in achieving speech impact.

5. *Productivity*. Speaking is always productive, which means that in the process of it a new product is created that did not entirely take place in the previous speech experience of the person (the trainee). Productivity is based on three psychophysiological mechanisms: reproduction, combination and transformation.

The reproduction mechanism works on the basis of memory. In the process of speaking, a person reproduces most phrases and many phrases. But the leading ones are the mechanisms of combination and transformation. The combination can be

carried out within the framework of phrases, phrases, text. It develops only with the constant use of new situations in training. The mechanism of transformation is closely related to it. As a result of his work, the speaker modifies a phrase (or part of it), pronounced or just appeared in his mind, but rejected on the basis of an assessment of its inadequacy to any factor: the listener's condition, tactical plans, etc.

The considered qualities of speaking as a product on the basis of their integration also determine the effectiveness of speaking. Listening and speaking are the types of speech activities that must be formed in students in order to provide an opportunity to communicate orally. Finally, it is participation in a conversation conducted in the classroom, which is possible only if you have an understanding of speech by ear, when the teacher and students speak on topics and situations provided for by the initial stage. The educational purpose of training. The educational purpose of the training is to form the skills to independently solve elementary communicative tasks in English within the framework of the topics proposed by the program, and to acquire elementary regional knowledge.

The realization of the educational goal of teaching a foreign language at school is associated with the expansion of the general educational horizons of students. Filling the teaching content with authentic information about the country of the language being studied, consistent reliance on the socio-cultural and speech experience of students in their native language the comparison of this experience with the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in a foreign language lesson are designed to form a broad understanding of the achievements of the cultures of their own people and the people of the country of the language being studied. Learning a foreign language helps to expand the general outlook of students, increases their culture.

In fact, familiarization with the language is also familiarization with the culture of the people who created it and who use it. "Language is considered in its two main functions: communicative – communication is carried out with its help and cumulative – it is the keeper of the culture of the people – its bearer". I believe that the educational goal of learning is as important as the communicative one, since when learning a foreign language, students get acquainted with English-speaking countries, with the culture of the peoples inhabiting them, their history, art, traditions, customs, literature, in other words, "touch" the cumulative function of language as the guardian of the culture of the people. But I believe that at the same time, the real needs and interests of younger schoolchildren in communication and cognition should be lost as much as possible. "The educational and developmental aspects of teaching a subject related to the formation of students' desire to master a foreign language as a means of

communication and interaction with another national culture and its native speakers are priority in primary school”. Students should feel the need to use a foreign language to solve communication problems, to carry out specific tasks in this or that area of knowledge and subject-practical activities relevant for primary school children. The inclusion of language in the summary of the life of a junior schoolboy is aimed at helping children realize that for a real acquaintance with the outside world, other countries, peoples and their customs and traditions, they need to speak and understand a foreign language well.

Learning a foreign language develops children’s thinking, emotions, attention, imagination, will, memory, as well as cognitive and linguistic abilities; forms a conscious attitude to both their native and foreign languages. Children develop interpersonal communication skills, self-control skills and control over the activities of other children. Teaching a foreign language contributes to the development of children, which was shown when revealing the educational purpose of learning. Educational and developmental goals are achieved in the process of practical mastery of a foreign language. Learning a foreign language forms a more attentive attitude among students to the forms of expression of thoughts, both in a foreign language and in their native language. “Where the teaching of the native language is well established, it is easier to teach a foreign language”. But although the opposite phenomenon can be observed. Well-organized English language teaching has a positive effect on the development of students’ thinking and speech abilities when teaching other humanities subjects and, above all, their native language.

Mastering a language outside the environment where it is spoken requires the creation of imaginary situations that can stimulate communication in the language being studied, and is associated with the development of imagination. Children of primary school age have a rich imagination, and, on the one hand, this ability should be used in the educational process, and on the other hand, reliance on this ability will further develop imagination and contribute to the creation and development of ideas. Improving the quality of teaching a foreign language in secondary school largely depends on what level of skills and abilities of students’ learning activities can be provided by modern methods of teaching foreign languages.

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